

Transnational Access project DelnVader

1. General information

Project acronym DelnVader

Project title DelnVader: Tracing the invasion of an exotic tree species in protected West-Mediterranean dune ecosystems

Type Scientific project

Scientific theme Detecting and analysing the spread of exotic Acacias in West-Mediterranean biodiverse coastal dunes with hyperspectral images and LiDAR

Main scientific field and Specific discipline Earth Sciences & Environment / Ecosystems & Biodiversity

Participants undertaking research

Name + link to id card	Research status	Email	Institution	Institution country	CV	Letter of reference	Publication
	Publication (1)						
BUTTSCHARDT Tillmann	Experienced researcher	buttschardt@uni-muenster.de	Universitaet Muenster	Germany			
HERTENSTEIN Florian	Undergraduate	f.hertenstein@uni-muenster.de		Germany			
		Publication (2)					
		Publication (1)					
PINHO Pedro	Undergraduate	ppinho@fc.ul.pt	Universidade de Lisboa - Faculdade de Ciências	Portugal			
PINTO Manuel	Technician	mpinto@fc.ul.pt	University of Lisbon	Portugal			
RASCHER Katie	Post-Graduate	katherine.grieve@uni-bielefeld.de	University of Bielefeld	Germany			Publication (2)
TATE Nicholas	Experienced researcher	njt9@le.ac.uk	University of Leicester	United Kingdom			Publication (1)
		Publication (1)					
UNGER Stephan	Post-doctoral researcher	stephan.unger@uni-bielefeld.de	University of Bielefeld	Germany			
WERNER Christiane	Experienced researcher	c.werner@uni-bayreuth.de	University Bayreuth	Germany			Publication (2)

Lead scientist's background

(scientific and aircraft measurements background and experience, English level) Graduate Assistant at the Institute of Landscape Ecology. Expertise in field methods of vegetation ecology including hemispherical photography. Research focus on applying remote sensing in assessing biological plant invasions.

English: Fluent

Portuguese: Fluent

French and Spanish: Basic
Experience of living abroad for several years.

Recent relevant publications by application group in last 5 years (up to 5)

- [Acacia longifolia invasion impacts vegetation structure and regeneration dynamics in open dunes and pine forests](#)
- [Combining vegetation indices, constrained ordination and fuzzy classification for mapping semi-natural vegetation units from hyperspectral imagery](#)
- [Competitive displacement or biotic resistance? Disentangling relationships between community diversity and invasion success of tall herbs and shrubs](#)
- [Estimating tree and stand variables in a Corsican Pine woodland from terrestrial laser scanner data](#)
- [On the use of phloem sap \$\delta^{13}C\$ as an indicator of canopy carbon discrimination](#)

Scientific problems being addressed by the experiments to be performed. Brief summary of the experiments Imaging spectroscopy enables to derive a specific spectral signature for individual objects which can be used to identify chemical and structural characteristics of e.g. plant foliage within and across ecosystems. LiDAR data can be used to assess landscape structure and especially to analyse stratified vegetation structure. We want to combine hyperspectral and LiDAR data to detect the spread of the exotic tree *Acacia longifolia* that is an "invasive engineer" in Portuguese dune ecosystems. It is able to fix atmospheric nitrogen, to alter the water cycle and to transform the vegetation structure. This causes various problems in many ecosystems worldwide.

To understand these ecosystem changes on landscape scale, precise data about *A. longifolia* distribution is necessary as baseline information. The invader occurs exposed to sky in the open dunes as well as in the undergrowth of dune forests. Local studies already show that it is able to facilitate its invasion by altering the ecosystem properties with negative impact on native and endemic species' and biodiversity.

This innovative approach of combining high resolution LiDAR and hyperspectral data is the appropriate way to track *A. longifolia* and to generate data of its distribution on landscape scale. Paralelly, this project draws on a huge amount of available information on *A. longifolia* at the local scale in Portugal and will just allow transporting this information (on strategy, behaviour, interaction) on the larger scale, thus allowing a new dimension of information on the invasive process, i.e. distribution and spatial trends of invasion stages.

Aircraft DO228 - NERC - ARSF

Why this aircraft best suits the experiments? Proposed alternative aircraft DO228-NERC-ARSF has the appropriate acquisition system including a photogrammetric camera, a Leica ALS 50-II LiDAR laser scanner and the Specim Eagle & Hawk Hyperspectral Scanner to generate the necessary high resolution LiDAR and hyperspectral data for plant species detection. As all these data can be collected simultaneously, using NERC's DO228 would be time and cost efficient.

In addition, this aircraft and its crew know the wider area of study, southern Portugal, already from a flight campaign in 2006 (EUFAR project STEPPEBIRD) which is an advantage regarding logistics and communication with air traffic control. The requested flight could be clustered with at least one other EUFAR TA-project, HyMedEcos-Gradients, which has been submitted recently and is a follow-up of the 2006 Steppebird project.

Last but not least, I know the aircraft, its crew, and the data provided by the aircraft's instruments from my participation of EUFAR's training summer school ADDRESS which took place in August 2010 in Hungary. As a result of the summer school's flight campaign and field work, a publication about detecting the exotic shrub *Elaeagnus angustifolia* (Russian Olive) in open grasslands and mixed with other shrubs and trees, and analyzing its invasive patterns on Tihany peninsula (Hungary) using and fusing hyperspectral and LiDAR data is in preparation. This publication is a joint work with my colleagues and participants of the ADDRESS summer school, Serdar Sürer and Toon Spanhove.

2. Description of the experiments

Scientific objectives / Proposed work / Anticipated output Invasive species can have a high impact on ecosystem services, biodiversity and ecosystem functioning (Rejmanek et al. 2005, Ehrenfeld 2010). Most recently, the fusion of high resolution hyperspectral and LiDAR data with ecological data has shown to be a powerful tool to detect invasive species and assess its impact in Tropical rainforests. Especially the combination of hyperspectral and structural (LiDAR) data is promising to be the decisive tool to detect an invader that also occurs in the understorey of forest (Asner 2008, Huang and Asner 2009) and thus cannot be easily detected using spectral data alone (e.g. Joshi et al 2006). To my knowledge this proposed project is the first study that combines hyperspectral and LiDAR remote sensing data with such fine spatial and spectral resolution with a variety of ecological ground data to detect an invasive species in Mediterranean open dunes and dune forests.

The principle objective of this project is to map the current spatial distribution of the ecosystem engineer *Acacia longifolia* in Mediterranean dune ecosystems, and to identify different stages of invasion in different invaded habitat types. This will be the baseline data to scale local impacts (e.g. Marchante et al. 2009, Rascher et al. in press, Werner et al. 2010, and references therein) of the invader up to landscape level. Desirable outcomes include observing impacts of nutrient enrichment due to *Acacia*'s nitrogen-fixation on surrounding vegetation and soil, and the remote sensing of stable isotope composition (see Wang et al. 2010) of *A. longifolia* and the surrounding vegetation to reveal impacts on ecosystem processes (see Werner et al. 2010 and references therein). Further important information will be gained on the species and functional type diversity as well as the biomass in the studied area to improve the land management schemes.

Airborne hyperspectral and LiDAR remote sensing data with a fine spectral and spatial (~1m and accordingly >5points/m²) resolution will be collected in the Nature Reserve of Santo André and Sancha, a Mediterranean dune ecosystem in South-West Portugal. Field spectra will be collected simultaneously for calibration purposes using an ASD FieldSpec pro. Samples of canopy leaves of *A. longifolia* and representative native shrubs will be taken and analysed for e.g. water content, Chlorophyll A, nitrogen, and tannin. *Acacia* populations at different stages of invasion, representative native shrub and tree and of other exotic tree species, and vegetation types will be mapped with a dGPS. Detailed digital distribution maps of protected plant species and vegetation types for further analysis are available.

This project could set the basis for studies on *A. longifolia* covering larger areas along the Portuguese coast. This project will also facilitate the monitoring of endangered, protected and diverse ecosystems worldwide (Richardson and Kluge 2008, Horus Institute 2005) by identifying areas that are vulnerable to invasions, lead to an early-detection scheme and evaluate *Acacia* control measures (see Huang and Asner 2009). Future projects could then up-scale even further using satellite data provided by German hyperspectral satellite mission EnMAP starting 2014. The processed data will be analysed using the software ENVI, eCognition and Polyworks (LiDAR only). Geospatial analysis will be conducted in ArcGIS. For vegetation analysis, we will use ordination software like Canoco and PCORD. Further statistical analyses, e.g. regression modelling, will be conducted with "R". The data will be archived at the Institute of Landscape Ecology of the University of Münster. Any participant is free to archive the data at her/his institute, too.

A large part of the results of this study will be published within my cumulative PhD thesis. As the applicant group is quite interdisciplinary and the available data will be quite large, we expect high publication output in different areas of research which will assure a broad dissemination of the results. The results will also be presented at conferences on (landscape) ecology, biological invasions and remote sensing. As the area of study is already subject to Master theses at the the Universities of Bielefeld, Lisbon and Münster, Bachelor and Master students will be involved and encouraged to use the data for their theses. The data and the results of this project can be included, in the future, for undergraduate and graduate classes in biology, ecology, modelling and remote sensing.

Bibliography

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Weather conditions (*e.g. clouds, atmospheric stability, wind speed and direction, weather...*) For imaging spectroscopy, "clear sky" conditions are preferred. Acceptable is a sky which is covered up to 1/8 by cumulus clouds. Not acceptable are cirrus clouds because the illumination conditions would vary too much for imaging spectroscopy.

The LIDAR measurements do not require these strict conditions, but as LIDAR and hyperspectral data will most likely be collected at the same time, there should be optimal weather conditions.

In the case that the acquisition of the LIDAR data fails for some reason while the collection hyperspectral data was successful, the LIDAR data can be collected another day when the illumination conditions are not perfect. Good, clear atmospheric conditions would deliver the best LiDAR results.

Time constraints (*time of the day, pass(es) of satellites, weekends, season...*) The flight should take place in March/April. This is the time when the invasive species in focus, *Acacia longifolia* is flowering which might enhance discrimination from the native species in the visible part of the spectra.

In addition, the flights shall take place between 2 hours before and 2 hours after local solar noon to guarantee sufficient illumination for imaging spectroscopy. 2.5 hours before/after solar noon might work as well if time is short (other projects, only few sunny days during a period of generally bad weather for the proposed time period, etc.).

The light conditions are more important for the acquisition of the hyperspectral than of the LiDAR data. For both data, clear atmospheric conditions are essential to get the best results.

Location(s) and reason for that choice Map of general area: [Project DelnVader: Map of general area](#)

The area of study consists mainly of the coastal dunes of the Nature Reserve "Lagoas de St. André e Sancha between Sines and Melides in Southwest Portugal. As the site is known from field trips, logistics such as accommodation and authorization for field work is assured. This area has been chosen for the following reasons:

The area has a high biodiversity value. It is very rich in species and landscape structures. Thus, it is protected by national (Reserva Natural das Lagoas de St^o André e da Sancha) and by European law (NATURA2000 habitat (PTCON0034) and partly by the bird directive (PTZPE0013, PTZPE0014)). Several rare and endemic plant species that are protected by national and European law (Annex II of the NATURA2000 directive) occur in this area. They are potentially threatened by the ecosystem changes caused by *Acacia longifolia*. There are detailed digital vegetation maps available for this area, and there is detailed knowledge about all occurring plant species. In addition, selected *A. longifolia* occurrences in different habitats (open dunes, dune forests with Pine or with Eucalyptus, *Acacia* shrublands) at different invasion stages (from establishing to dominating) have been mapped with Trimble dGPS for ground truthing. This map will be extended for the flight campaign. Historical photographs for this site are available which allow a sound comparison of the historical and mapped distribution of *A. longifolia*.

The Geographic Institute of the Portuguese military (IGeoE) has been informed about a planned flight campaign in this area and there were no concerns mentioned.

Within the area of study there are sufficient reference targets for atmospheric correction such as roads, parking areas, sandy beaches, lagoons, buildings, that will be also suitable as dGPS-based ground control points for later georegistration

Number of flights / flight hours and flight patterns We estimate one flight with a flight time of 2h at an estimated data acquisition speed of 4km/min and a turn time between the lines of 3 minutes and 15 lines in total. The swath width for the Hawk would be 450m with an overlap of 100m (50m at each side).

The flight shall take place at 1000m altitude at "clear sky" conditions between 2 hours before and after local noon in mid April.

A lower altitude to get a higher spatial resolution would be desired. This would lead to more flight lines and more flight hours. This has to be discussed with the aircraft operator.

The flight lines are orientated within the solar plane to guarantee best illumination conditions. The North-South extension of the indicated area of study is the required size and should not be diminished. The E-W extension is minimum 1km and maximum 5km. This covers *Acacia longifolia* invasion at different stages and in different habitat types within the Nature Reserve "Lagoas de Santo André e Sancha". It also incorporates important references for atmospheric corrections and dGPS-based ground control points.

The NS extension should not be altered, the EW extension of the area of study can be altered within the mentioned dimension (covering a 3km wide coastal dune strip) if the flight lines were not lying within the solar plane, but parallel to the coast to safe flight lines. In the latter case, one flight perpendicular to the coastline would be needed for BRDF corrections.

Other constraints or requirements The remote sensing department of the Portuguese Geographic Institute of the Military (IGeoE) has been contacted about the flight campaign already. There should be no restrictions.

Access to field equipment (ASD Field Spectrometer) is still needed.

A senior researcher with available field equipment has been contacted. I will also contact the colleagues I know from the EUFAR ADDRESS summer school in Hungary 2010. Equipment and expertise of parallel flight campaigns could be shared. Further help from within the EUFAR network would be desired.

From 11th to 13th April 2011, the 7th Workshop on Imaging Spectroscopy organized the European Association of Remote Sensing Laboratories (EARSel) will take place. Some of the participating scientists will attend this meeting. A flight during those days is basically not preferred, however if it would be the only possible flight window a plausible solution.

3. Key measurements required to achieve science aims

Parameter / measurement required ALS50-II instrument specification:

- FOV: 40 deg.

- elevation point cloud in LAS and ASCII file format

- Multi return height intensity signals

- point density: >5 points/m²; the more, the better as single tree/shrub detection is one of the main targets using lidar in this study;

As the points density is a very crucial point in this study, a no calculator for the point density could be found on the aircraft operator's webpage as e.g. for the Eagle/Hawk instruments, the set-up for the Lidar instrument (FOV, flight altitude) has to be discussed with the aircraft operator.

Images from the RCD105 digital camera

Full-range Hyperspectral eagle and hawk data, post-processed (NASA level 1b) from the aircraft operator spectral binning can be applied to improve the quality of the data

AISA Eagle specification

- Ground pixel size: 0.7m at 1000 altitude

AISA Hawk Specification

- Ground pixel size: 1.3m at 1000 altitude

A smaller ground pixel size is desired. As this incorporates a lower flight altitude and more flight lines, this has to be checked with the aircraft operator.

Generally, a fine spectral and a fine spatial resolution are required. Thus the acquisition of the Lidar and the hyperspectral data including the flight patterns need further discussion between the research and the aircraft operator team.

If applicable, specify TA instrument required None

Instruments to be provided by hosting aircraft operator (*basic instrumentation owned by the aircraft operator described on EUFAR website only*) AISA Eagle/Hawk hyperspectral sensor

LEICA ALS50-II LIDAR

Leica RCD 105 Digital Photogrammetric Camera

Instruments to be provided by scientific group (*Have already been flown. On which aircraft? Do the instruments have their own data acquisition system?*) Trimble dGPS (1 unit)

ASD Field Spectrometer (requested)

ENVI Image Processing Software

Polyworks (Lidar processing software)

eCognition (Imaging Processing Software)

ArcGIS (Geospatial Analysis software)

PcORD, CANOCO (ordination software for vegetation data)

Lab facilities including basic chemical analysis of the soil and plant leaves and stable isotopes and near-infrared reflectance spectroscopy calibrations.

Facilities to analyze the age of *Acacia longifolia* by tree ring analysis are available, a dendrochronological/ecological study about *Acacia longifolia* is in progress and a study to analyse more occurring shrubs and trees and to reveal size-age relationships is planned.

Instrument operators onboard (in addition to those provided by the aircraft operator). If so, how many?

If applicable, plans for simultaneous field work plans / ground equipment to be used A Trimble dGPS is available for ground truthing at the Institute of Landscape Ecology, University of Münster. Reference sites of the vegetation types including different stages of invasion by *Acacia longifolia* and different invaded habitats (canopy building in the open dunes and dominating the understorey in the forests) within the area of study were already mapped with the Trimble dGPS during a field campaign in September/October 2010. These previously identified reference sites will allow for effective field work since logistics can be optimized for reference checking.

Parallel to the flight, an ASD Field Spectrometer will be used to collect field spectra for ground truthing of the different vegetation types including different stages of invasion by *A. longifolia* across different invaded habitats. Field spectra will also be taken of native species canopies close and far away from *A. longifolia* to analyze the enrichment of neighbouring plants by nitrogen-fixing *A. longifolia*. Plant samples will be collected for further chemical analyses in the labs of the participant group (N,P,K, stable isotopes, lignin, cellulose, tannin, chlorophyll). A terrestrial laser scanner, Optech ILRIS-3D, will be used in the field to improve terrain modelling via airborne laser scanning data interpretation.

Digital hemispherical photographs will be applied to analyse and model the light conditions and the Leaf Area Index to add to the vegetation and canopy structure analysis with LIDAR data.

4. Data processing and analysis

Methodology for handling the data and analysis of output (*airborne data acquisition, ground-truthing / observations, data processing and interpretation*) The flight at an altitude of 1000m or less will generate hyperspectral data with a spatial resolution of about 1m. The LiDAR data with its high point density (> 5 points/m²) for single tree selection will deliver fine resolution data about the vegetation and canopy structure. The ground truth data will consist of field spectral data for calibration, dGPS mapped *Acacia longifolia* individuals and populations, dGPS mapped native shrubs and trees including data about plant individual height, crown size, phenological state and growth form, and dGPS mapped vegetation types, the results of the chemical analysis of the leaf samples and the chemical analysis of sap flow including isotope analysis of selected *Acacia* and overstorey trees to characterize the canopy chemistry in addition to leaf analysis. The vegetation types will be characterized by plot-based description of species cover for every vegetation layer. The plots will be selected by stratified random sampling. The selection of the sub-units of the study area will be based on experience of earlier field work and aerial photograph interpretation. The raw data will be atmospherically corrected and then georeferenced. There are sufficient reference targets for the remote sensing data in the area of study (e.g. sandy plains, lagoons, car parkings, buildings, roads). Additional, artificial targets (coloured boards with standard reflection properties) will be laid out at site and mapped with the dGPS for referencing.

The key questions is that if by fusing fine resolution LiDAR, fine resolution hyperspectral and detailed ecological data a distribution map of *A. longifolia* in open dunes and dune forest can be generated, and if different stages of invasion can be identified. Furthermore, a question is if the nitrogen enrichment of neighbouring plants and the alteration of the vegetation structure and the above ground biomass by *A. longifolia* can be observed. Differences in biomass and diversity of invaded and non-invaded sites can be calculated.

Ground truth data have been retrieved in various projects of the participants such as historical photographs, digital vegetation maps, selected dGPS-mapped vegetation types and *A. longifolia* invasion stages, selected dGPS-mapped *A. longifolia* populations and selected analyses on *A. longifolia* and native species' leaf chemistry. Digital hemispherical photography and ground-based LiDAR data Optech's ILRIS 3D terrestrial laser scanner will be applied to improve the knowledge and the calibration of the vegetation and canopy structure (vegetation density, light conditions, leaf area index). A project to derive the age of *A. longifolia* by stem disk analysis and relating this to height, crown size and above ground biomass is in progress.

Analysis of the spatial distribution of *A. longifolia* including the historical landuse derived from historical aerial photographs can help to identify the triggers and the limits of its invasion, and lead to and map vulnerable sites susceptible to future invasions. In a possible future project, this study could be extended to other sites along the Portuguese coast to analyse the influence of the pronounced climatic gradient between northern and southern Portugal which is often discussed as a very important factor of *A. longifolia* invasions.

When regarding *A. longifolia* as a model for an invasive species, the results of this study can be related to invasive species with similar characteristics such as growth form, fixation of atmospheric nitrogen, invasion on nutrient poor soils, especially when occurring in the understorey of forests.

The data will be analysed using the appropriate software for image analysis (ENVI, eCognition), for LiDAR data modelling and visualization (Polyworks), for ordination of the vegetation data (CANOCO, PcOrd, R) and geospatial analysis (ArcGIS, R).

Resources available to support the project beyond the flying/data acquisition period (*funding, cooperation with other projects, manpower for analysis of results and preparation of user report, availability of laboratory facilities...*) The equipment to conduct the field work and the data analysis, the authorization to access the field sites and the laboratory facilities (basic chemical analyses of soils and plants, stable isotopes, Near-infrared spectroscopy) will be provided within by the participating research institutions.

I received a grant by the German DAAD to conduct field from January to June 2011 in Portugal. So I can prepare, conduct and perform follow-up work on the ground.

This project is an add-on to long term studies (supported by DAAD, DFG, and FCT grants) conducted by the University of Lisbon and Bielefeld, and since 2007 including the University of Münster, about *Acacia longifolia* in Portuguese dune ecosystems.

Current projects are:

"Changing ground water levels: the impact on an invasive species and native plant communities in a Mediterranean dune ecosystem" (TransDune, DFG, WE2681/3-1),

"Impact of an invasive species on water relations and plant community functioning in a Mediterranean dune ecosystem" (D/08/13009) Bilateral cooperation (Accoes integradas/DAAD) of Jun'Prof. C. Werner and Dr. C. Máguas (Bielefeld, Lisbon),

"Effects of marine influence on the foredune vegetation: study of the ecophysiology and water resources using isotopic analysis" (CGL2008-10577, Spain).

In addition, the Universities of Bielefeld, Lisbon and Münster in cooperation with their partners at the Federal University of Vicosa, Brazil, are negotiation with the EU for Marie Curie Staff Exchange Call to set up a network to study *Acacia longifolia* invasion worldwide. To extend this network, Prof. David Richardson from the Centre for Invasion Biology, University of Stellenbosch, South Africa, has been contacted to cooperate on studies about *A. longifolia*.

This project also adds-on to vegetation studies conducted by the Portuguese Institute of Nature Conservation and Biodiversity (INCB) in collaboration with Manuel Joao Pinto (Botanical Garden, University of Lisbon) in the Santo André and Sancha Lagoons Nature Reserve in the South of the area of study. This project will contribute to a management scheme to protect the endemic, endangered and protected species of the area and to control *A. longifolia* invasion.

The analysis of the remote sensing data will mainly be subject to my PhD project, but the participation of Master and Bachelor students from the different participating research institutes is planned as every institute has its own expertise which can contribute significantly to the success of this project.

5. Planning

Starting date: 08-04-2011

Ending date: 08-04-2011

Preferred and acceptable dates (*season / time windows*) Preferred: April 2011

Acceptable: March, April, May 2011

If the time for review is too short, the flight could be delayed. The latest date would be March/April 2011. A flight in summer/autumn 2010 is possible, but would need to be discussed with the applicant and the aircraft operator. I just have been contacted by researchers who would like to apply for a LiDAR flight at a Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) site in Coruche, 70km northeast of Lisbon. They would need land surface structure data and calibrate these data with their isotope and carbon flux measurement from their Eddy covariance tower.

Agreement to share aircraft time (*project clustering, cost sharing*) Yes

6. Other useful comments

Training benefit of the project (e.g. spread potential of airborne research to a wide scientific community; training of research students in experimental planning, methodology, data analysis and applications, etc) The group of participant consists of research institutions of different areas (Biology, Ecophysiology, Applied Landscape Ecology, Ecosystem Research). National authorities of remote sensing, forestry and nature conservation in Portugal have asked to join the campaign.

There is a long lasting exchange of researchers including PhD, Master and Bachelor students between the Universities of Bielefeld, Lisbon, and since recently, the University of Münster. The exchange were and are mainly funded by the DAAD personal and travel grants, DFG and FCT projects and EU Erasmus student exchanges. Recently, there was a field trip of the work group of Münster with Master students to study Acacia longifolia invasion in Portugal advertising the possible upcoming EUFAR flight campaign.

It is intended to publish the results at upcoming international conferences about Ecology, Remote Sensing or Biological Invasions.

The flight campaign will also be a subject of the exchange network between the Universities of Bielefeld, Lisbon, Münster and Vicosa (Brazil) to study Acacia invasion worldwide. The University of Stellenbosch (South Africa) and the University of Coimbra (Portugal) have also been contacted and will be part of the network soon.

The data set can be used in master and bachelor courses to show up-to-date possibilities of the application of remote sensing data in ecological studies.

The results of this project may inspire new ideas to study A. longifolia invasion in Northern Portugal and worldwide (e.g. Brazil, South Africa). A. longifolia can be seen as a "model invader" and the knowledge can also inspire similar projects to study invasive species and ecosystem processes.

As I participated in the 1st FP7 EUFAR Training Course "Advanced Digital Remote sensing in Ecology and earth Sciences Summer School" (ADDRESS) in August 2010 in Hungary where the students were taught how to apply LiDAR and hyperspectral data in ecological studies, and where the students were repeatedly encouraged to apply for a flight within via "Transnational Access", this proposed flight would directly connect to EUFAR's commitment to promote young scientists. If the intended follow-up workshop of the ADDRESS summer school will take place next summer, then the preliminary results could be presented there, too. I will contact my colleagues from the ADDRESS summer school if they would like to participate in the proposed campaign.

If possible, 3 scientific reviewers that EUFAR may contact Dr. Peter Burai

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Sources of funding of the project and of related projects (if clustering with existing projects supported either by national or other EC funding, how the project add additional or complementary aims to the already funded experiments) In all existing projects, the focus is in the impact on the impact of Acacia longifolia on the diversity, structure and the ecosystem processes local scale.

This project will provide for the first time the required data to analyze A.longifolia's impact on landscape scale.

It fits in very well with my PhD project as I am funded in Germany so far by my working, as in Portugal I will be funded by the DAAD and in Brazil I will be funded by the EU IRSES Programm. My work group will apply together with our colleagues from the University of Bielefeld for a DFG project to sustain my funding (salary) and to install a counterpart at the Biological Faculty in Bielefeld. The EUFAR project would complement very well this funding: our field work is basically funded, but there is no funding for a flight campaign. This EUFAR project would fit it perfectly and complement the current projects, especially my PhD project, very well.

Scientific training provided by lead scientist to other EUFAR sponsored scientists within the fields of the proposed experiments and analysis Yes

Number of students 3

Number of days recommended 14

Knowledge about EUFAR opportunities from Advertisement at conferences/scientific events

Related documents

You may need to login to the EUFAR Back Office to see all the documents.

7. Reporting

Campaign dates: From 04-04-2011 to 08-04-2011

Participants

Name	First time flying this aircraft	Participation in the campaign	Number of visits to campaign	Duration of stay	T&S reimbursed	Additional information
GROSSE-STOLTE NBERG Andre	Yes	On site	1	25	Yes	
ANTUNES Cristina	Yes	On site	1	8	Yes	
BUTTSCHARDT Tillmann	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	
HASSAN Ahmed	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	
HELLMANN Christine	Yes	On site	1	25	Yes	
HERTENSTEIN Florian	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	

MGUAS HANSON Cristina	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	
OLDELAND Jens	Yes	On site	1	12	Yes	
PINHO Pedro	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	
PINTO Manuel	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	
RASCHER Katie	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	
TATE Nicholas	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	
THIELE Jan	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	
UNGER Stephan	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	
WERNER Christiane	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	

Meetings

Start date	End date	Location	Title	Number of persons from the group attending the meeting	Overall number of attendees
14-03-2011	14-03-2011	Lisbon/Gloucest	Pre-meeting	1	7

Confirmation of the user access (list of flights, number of flight hours) / Evaluation of the service provided by the operator: mark (1-Unsatisfactory, 2-Insufficient, 3-Satisfactory, 4-Good, 5-Excellent) and comments

4 - good The time frame for the 4 scheduled campaigns was quite tight, in my opinion, as the acquisition of hyperspectral data heavily depends on weather conditions. The operator dealt very well with the stressful situation around the flight (the LiDAR sensor needed to be replaced, a dust cloud from Morocco came along). The post-campaign meeting is still due as Andre Grosse-Stoltenberg (PI) was not able to work last summer/autumn due to health reasons, so we are a bit behind schedule.

Quality of data and associated service

We still have to have a closer look at the data (see above "The post-campaign meeting ..."). So we cannot comment on the associated service, either. So far, we received the data including reports on data quality which looks fine.

Main achievements / Further plans for analysis

We have a really nice data set now consisting of gps and spectral ground truth data as well as plant samples for chemical analysis. The big task will be now to fuse the airborne data (Lidar, hyperspectral) with the field data (GPS ground truth, hyperspectral plant data) and the Lab data (plant samples) to identify the presence and quantity the impact of the studied invasive tree species on ecosystem services and functioning in our area of study.

Difficulties encountered

An open question was: What would happen if the PI cancels the flight due to insufficient weather conditions, or non-functioning of aircraft equipment (e.g. Lidar sensor)? Would EUFAR pay the operator to conduct another flight? Would EUFAR pay T&S twice? When would a possible new flight take place? Providing ground equipment such as an ASD field spec, or providing funding for rent would help newcomers in the field of hyperspectral remote sensing. Some of the students who were on the project in the beginning, were not on the project half a year later when the campaign took place. It is not unusual that a student changes plans (e.g. for studying abroad, due to obligatory lectures or practical at the home institution, ...). But then we could not just put another student on the project, and just swap the names, which made planning the campaign and the crew difficult. In another case, somebody wanted to send the assistant, which was not possible, either. A bit more flexibility to swap the people on the project would help here. Higher funding for T&S would be desirable to include more participants, especially the students.

Publications linked to the project

Website of the project